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Research Article

AWARENESS ABOUT WEANING IN SOCIETY¹Dr. Raza Ali saif, ²Abeera Hameed, ³Dr. Muhammad Arslan Ibrahim¹Sahiwal Medical College Sahiwal Punjab Pakistan,²BVH Bahawalpur,³Mayo Hospital Lahore**Abstract**

Introduction: weaning means soft food given to a child after breastfeeding. it is as important as breastfeeding because it provides essential minerals and vitamins which are essential for body growth and brain development. It is given at the age of 4 to 6 months. Children who don't take breast milk can be started weaning at the age of 4 months. it provides nutrition to child so that he may be able to gain weight according to age. Children who start weaning late like after one year become low weight for age and it affect them whole of life. This research was not only assess the public knowledge about weaning but also spread awareness in mothers. Whole climate was friendly.

Objectives: aims and objectives behind this research are to exclude that how much people know about its importance and to provide them awareness about weaning

Research design and methodology: It was a cohort study. Sample data was selected by randomized trial.

Venue: DHQ Teaching Hospital Sahiwal Punjab Pakistan.

Conclusion; 69% mothers start weaning at proper time at the age of 4 to 6 months. Children who took weaning at 1 year or late 29% of them suffer health problems like Diarrhea, RTI etc.

Keywords: weaning, breastfeeding, child body, growth, low weight.

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QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

The importance of weaning can't be ignored for health of a child. Weaning is the early diet given to baby after breastfeeding. It is soft food comprising banana, egg yolk, egg white, cerelac, dalia, khichri etc. It is usually started at 6 months but can also be given from 4 months. Children having weaning maintain their health through out life. If they don't take proper weaning become malnourished and low weight.

Start of weaning at 6 months is done by soft food then as he grows and of age 10 month then can be given solid food as the child is weaned he starts to gain weight and weaning also provides him essential nutrients. Weaning reduces the hunger and requirement of milk.

Due to its importance we decided to make a research to know about general awareness in society and introduce that weaning is a regular chapter in the life of a child. If we want to see our generation healthy, wealthy and wise. Research was conducted at peads opd DHQ teaching hospital sahiwal.

Objectives

There were two main objectives;

- i) To know about awareness of weaning in our society
- ii) To introduce the concept and importance to parents about weaning

Literature review**Weaning**

It is introducing food other than milk. Usually it is taken in the context of addition of semisolid feed to the infants diet. Infants should be weaned at 4 to 6 months of age. When solid foods are introduced, single ingredient foods should be chosen and started one at a time at weekly intervals to permit the identification of food intolerance. After 4 months, neuromuscular development has advanced sufficiently to pureed

solids can be swallowed. By 8 to 10 months, the infant accepts finely chopped foods and likelihood of choking is decreased. Nuts and hard candies should not be given until later in childhood. At one year child requires 3 meals/day and two snacks in between. Weaning include micro and macro nutrients. Micronutrients include vitamins and minerals. Macronutrients include carbohydrates, proteins and fats. So weaning is important for growth because vitamins essential for growth can not be synthesized at all in body.

Research design and methodology**Study design**

It is cross sectional type of study

Venue

OPD peads department DHQ teaching hospital Sahiwal

Data collection

A randomly self designed questionnaire was used to collect data from parents in opd

Questionnaire

A structured questionnaire was formulated after extensive struggle and hard working

It comprises of two portions;

- i) 1st portion contains name, father name, age and introduction
- ii) 2nd portion contains questions related to weaning

Inclusion criteria

All the children presented in opd

Exclusion criteria

Parents who refused to give consent or children in a critical condition not included in research

Sample size

Total sample size of 181 patients

Ethics approval

Prior to questionnaire, informed consent was obtained from parents after assuring confidentiality

Data presentation, analysis and interpretation**1) Demographic data****i) age groups**

Age group	number	%
< 2 year	92	51
>2 year	89	49

iii) Gender

Gender	Number	%
Male	100	55
Female	81	45

2. Educational data

i) when you started weaning?

69% children started weaning at 6 months

18% started weaning at 1 year

13% started weaning at > 1 year

iii) children who started weaning after at 1 year or late were healthy or sick?

70% were healthy

30% were sick and low weight for age

iv) What you include weaning? Dalia,rice,khichri or all

95% women said that weaning include dalia,khichri,rice,bread and othersoft food
5% women said that they give only dalia

iv)why the child not taking weaning?

70% children were not provided weaning so they started late
15% children don't like
5% children were sick

CONCLUSION:

After all this we concluded that

i) 69% percent mothers started weaning at proper time. these mothers were actually educated by health

care professionals or were teachers or belong to educated families. these babies were healthy, gaining weight according to age rarely.

ii) 29% Child who don't take weaning at proper time suffer nutrition and health problems later in life. out of 181 children 29 were given weaning at 1 year and 22 were given at > one year. these who were started weaning late suffer from health problems like respiratory tract infections, diarrhea, low weight for age

iii) Out of 58 children who started weaning late 41 of them were healthy like normal children and 17 remained sick off and on. it means weaning affected 30% children.

iv) Why the weaning was started late? Causes include misconceptions, lack of knowledge, poverty etc. Mainly mothers were not aware of its importance.

v) We were pleased to know that 95% mothers who were giving weaning their children include all items in soft diet like dalia, khichri, egg etc.

vi) Children who take weaning at proper time maintain their body weight.

vii)

SUGGESTIONS:

i) There should be an arrangement to spread awareness of weaning so that we be able to improve the health of our young generation

ii) Health care professionals can play an important role in this regard. these include doctors, nurses, dispensers, lhv, lhws, mid wives etc.

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